

Agroforestry in Greece

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Inventory of problems for each region and how was it solved
- Factsheets: current policy an AF at regional level
- Bureaucracy: management and processing usually at slow pace, administrative forms tedious
- Legal framework non dynamic. Regulation non adapted to new productive and processing models

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	Greece		Agrisilviculture	0,14%	0,28%
Nut level:	-		Agrosilvopasture	0,03%	0,02%
Eurostat code:	EL		Kitchen gardens	0,28%	0,16%
Area (km ²):	130.048		Holding type	2016	2023
Population	2018	2022	Natural person (ha)	3.138.840	-
Population	10.667.336	10.461.627	Legal person (ha)	13.760	-
Density (p km ⁻²)	82	80	Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	-	-
Cover data	2018	2022	Natural person (holder)	684.240	-
Forest	37,77%	27,07%	Legal person (holder)	650	-
Arable land	12,01%	8,17%	Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	-	-
Permanent crops	1,01%	1,25%	Regional Used Agricultural Area	2016	2023
Agroforestry	18,63%	25,35%	Farm number	684.890	-
Shrubland	8,28%	16,26%	Farm ha (UAA)	3.152.580	-
Grassland	12,65%	11,51%	Animal populations (Thousand head)	2018	2023
Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022	Live bovine animals	542	639
Silvopasture	18,18%	24,90%			

Dairy cows	95	88
Non dairy cows	174	166
Live swine, domestic species	722	771
Live sheep	8.435	7.994
Live goats	3.631	2.836

CROPS (Hectares) 2016 2023

Utilised agricultural area	3.152.580	-
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)	906.380	-
Common wheat and spelt	160.740	-
Durum wheat	397.660	-
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)	15.950	-
Barley	105.300	-
Oats and spring cereal mixtures	63.890	-
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix	115.920	-
Rice	30.950	-
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain	31.610	-
Industrial crops	342.590	-
Cotton seed and fibre	231.480	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.	1.140	-
Fibre crops	-	-
Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants	3.190	-
Plants harvested green from arable land	289.660	-
Green maize	29.700	-

Kitchen gardens	7.040	-
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Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	2
Forestry	1
Crop diversification including woody perennials	1
Crop rotation including woody perennials	0
Livestock including woody perennials	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	0
Woody perennials to add organic matter	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	0
Animal welfare using woody perennials	0
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	0
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	0
Interventions	2

María Rosa Mosquera Losada, Ana Couso Viana, Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro, Nuria Ferreiro Domínguez & José Javier Santiago Freijanes (2025) Universidade de Santiago de Compostela

References

- Coverland data and Agroforestry practice cover: EUROSTAT LAND COVER/USE STATISTICS (LUCAS). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/lucas/database/primary-data>
- Demographics and Farmland data: Eurostat, <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>
- Area by NUTS 3 region (demo_r_d3area) https://doi.org/10.2908/REG_AREA3
- Population on 1 January by age, sex and NUTS 2 region (demo_r_d2jan) https://doi.org/10.2908/DEMO_R_D2IAN
- Key farm variables area livestock (LSU) labour force and standard output (SO) by agricultural size of farm (UAA) legal status of holding and NUTS 2 regions (ef_kvaareg) https://doi.org/10.2908/EF_KVAAREG
- Farms and hectares by crops, utilised agricultural area, economic size of the farm and NUTS 2 region [ef_lus_allcrops_custom_21007488] https://doi.org/10.2908/EF_LUS_ALLCROPS
- Animal populations (December) by NUTS 2 regions [agr_r_animal] https://doi.org/10.2908/AGR_R_ANIMAL
- CAP Strategic Plans by country https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/cap-strategic-plans_en#cap-strategic-plans-by-country